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Abstract

Low-temperature waste heat below 200°C generated from nature, industry, and the human body exists everywhere, but is easily discarded due to a lack of technology to recover it. Thermogalvanic cells based on ion transport are inexpensive devices that directly convert heat into electricity and are flexible in material selection. Carbon nanomaterials are known to have excellent properties as thermogalvanic cell electrodes due to their large specific surface area and fast electron transport properties. This study explores the potential application of nitrogen-doped (N-doped) oxidized carbon nanotubes with melamine as thermogalvanic cell electrodes.

Introduction

Low-grade heat

- Low-grade heat is abundant and ubiquitous but is generally discarded owing to a lack of cost-effective recovery technologies.
- To efficiently recover low-grade waste heat, thermoelectric technology offers an approach to convert heat directly into electrical energy without moving parts or audible noise.

Thermogalvanic cell

- A disadvantage of solid-state thermoelectric devices is that their performance relative to cost has so far limited their application for waste heat recovery and they are expensive due to the use of rare elements.
- Thermogalvanic cells, also called thermo-cells, that utilize ion transport, provide a cost-effective solution for converting heat directly into electricity and present flexible device options for a variety of applications.
- To improve the performance of thermogalvanic cells, carbon nanomaterials with fast redox processes, high thermal and electrical conductivity, and high gravimetric surface area are selected.

Nitrogen-doped (N-doped) oxidized SWCNTs with melamine

- In this study, we aimed to prepare electrodes with reduced charge transfer resistance by utilizing the improved electrical conductivity and increased specific surface area of N-doped oxidized CNTs and use them in a thermo-cell.

Experimental

Defect introduction into SWCNTs

1. Purification (acid treatment)

- Acid: H₂SO₄/HNO₃ solution (volume ratio of 3:1 = H₂SO₄:HNO₃)
- Method: sonication (6 h)

2. Introduction of defects and oxidation

- Acid: H₂SO₄, KMnO₄
- Method: stirring

3. Nitrogen-doping

- Nitrogen source: Melamine (SWCNT:melamine 1:8)
- Method: stirring (12 h) tip sonication (12 h)
- Thermal treatment:
 - ramping rate (10 °C/min)
 - target temperature (800 °C)
 - duration time (2 h)

Thermo-electrochemical cell

1. Cell components

- 5 mm thick spacer
- Electrolyte: 0.4 M K₃Fe(CN)₆/K₄Fe(CN)₆
- Active electrodes: Pristine CNT, KMnO₄ treated CNT, N-doped CNT (stirring, tip sonication)

2. Temperature

- Hot source/Cold sink T: 45/15 °C
- ΔT between active electrodes: 15.1-16.1 °C

Summary

- We chose a thermocell for harvesting low-grade heat and utilized N-doped oxidized SWCNTs as electrodes to reduce charge transfer resistance.
- Mixing CNT and melamine by tip sonication led to a significant reduction in internal resistance and improved thermocell performance, likely due to the synergistic interaction between the increased Graphitic-N content and oxygen functional groups on the CNT surface.

Result & Discussion

- Four different types of electrodes were analyzed: pristine SWCNTs, SWCNTs with increased surface area achieved by introducing defects through KMnO₄ treatment, and nitrogen-doped oxidized SWCNTs prepared using two different melamine mixing methods (stirring and tip sonication).

Structure analysis

Raman Spectroscopy

- After KMnO₄ treatment, defects and functional groups are formed on the CNT surface, which reduces the G/D ratio. *Phys. Status Solidi B* 2019, 256, 1800742
- N-doped SWCNTs showed reduced D band and increased G/D ratio compared to KMnO₄-treated SWCNTs. This indicates that defects can be rearranged towards the formation of sp²-bound SWCNTs after heat treatment under N₂ atmosphere. *Chemical Physics Letters* 424 (2006) 345-352
- If melamine was mixed with SWCNTs, the use of tip sonication resulted in the introduction of more defects compared to stirring, leading to a further decrease in the G/D ratio.

X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS)

- When melamine was mixed with SWCNT through stirring and heat treated, the N atomic % was 6.43, and when mixed and heat treated through tip sonication, it was 4.51. Stirring resulted in a Pyridinic-N content approximately twice that of Graphitic-N, while tip sonication produced similar amounts of both nitrogen species.

Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM)

- In pristine SWCNTs, large bundles are observed due to the influence of van der Waals interactions, and after KMnO₄ treatment, the bonding effect is reduced due to defects formed on the surface, leading to the exfoliation of CNT bundles. *Appl. Sci.* 2021, 11, 8452, *Surfaces and Interfaces* 14 (2019) 1-8
- Compared to the KMnO₄ treated samples, the N-doped samples exhibit larger bundles and the tip sonication method tends to shorten the CNTs with longer processing times, resulting in a rougher surface compared to the stirred samples. *Nanomaterials* 2021, 11, 1469

Thermo-electrochemical cell test

Voltage-current and power density

- N-doped oxidized SWCNTs made by tip sonication showed an enhanced current and power density while stirring exhibited poor performance.

Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS), Internal resistance

- Tip sonication method reduced the internal and charge transfer resistances of CNT electrode by 73% and 93%, respectively. This is likely attributed to the synergistic interaction between the elevated Graphitic-N content and oxygen functional groups on the CNT surface, which will be explored in future studies.